

Simple Superluminal Entangled Communication and Its Base of Complete Special Relativity, Extensive Special Relativity and Quantum Theory

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Abstract

Based on quantum entanglement and corresponding quantum communication, first we research a simple superluminal entangled communication scheme, whose key is to establish two mutually entangled particles or devices A and B. We observe and control the information of A position, then can know the corresponding results of the other B. This is not to send directly information each other. It may be superluminal. Next, in special relativity we provided that there are necessarily two symmetrical topological structures separated by the light-cone, which includes the generalized Lorentz transformation (GLT) for the spacelike interval, in which phase velocity is superluminal. This complete special relativity is base of this scheme, and should agree and test GLT. Further, it may be developed to the extensive special relativity, in which only $c \rightarrow c_h$ (another invariant velocity). Third, we research the entanglement as macroscopic field and some predictions. This scheme is combined between the special relativity and quantum theory. Finally, we proposed the extensive quantum theory and its applications.

Keywords: quantum, entanglement, communication, superluminal, special relativity, prediction, extension.

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Introduction

Based on the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) correlations and Bell inequalities, current new experiments validated that quantum mechanics possesses the nonlocality and entangled state, etc.

First, Aspect, et al. (1982a,b), realized EPR experiment by the measure on the linear-polarization correlation of pairs of photons emitted in a radiative cascade of calcium and time-varying analyzers, and it agrees with the quantum mechanical predictions and the greatest violation of generalized Bell inequalities. Ghosh, et al. (1987), demonstrated the existence of nonclassical effects in the interference of two

photons.

In 2022 Nobel Prize in Physics three winners are A. Aspect, J. Clauser and A. Zeilinger for the entangled experiments and quantum information. Aspect speculated that quantum entanglement would trigger a technological revolution. In this chapter, we research a simple superluminal entangled communication scheme, and its base is the complete special relativity, in which phase velocity is superluminal. This scheme is combined between the special relativity and quantum theory.

General Quantum Communication

First, Bennett, et al. (1993), proposed the

quantum teleportation via dual classical information and nonclassical EPR correlations. This basic method forms base of the quantum communication discussed widely. Then Bouwmeester, et al. (1997), investigated experimental quantum teleportation, in which an initial photon which carries the polarization that is to be transferred and one of a pair of entangled photons are subjected to a measurement such that the second photon of the entangled pair acquires the polarization of the initial photon. This latter photon can be arbitrarily far away from the initial one. Pan, et al. (1998), realized experimentally entangled freely propagating particles that never physically interacted with one another or which have never been dynamically coupled by any other means. Further, they researched entanglement and quantum communication (Pan, et al. 2001;2003).

Weihs, et al. (1998), observed strong violation of Bell's inequality in an EPR-type experiment with independent observers. This experiment the first time fully enforced the condition of locality, and the necessary spacelike separation of the observations is achieved by sufficient physical distance between the measurement stations, by ultrafast and random setting of the analyzers, and by completely independent data registration.

Gao (2004) analyzed the relation between quantum collapse, consciousness and superluminal communication. Quantum collapse as result of quantum nonlocality may permit the realization of quantum superluminal communication (QSC). He introduced a possible mechanism of nonlinear quantum evolution and achieved QSC, which must exist based on the quantum nonlocal influence (Gao 2014). Walleczek, et al. (2016), discussed the apparent conflict between quantum mechanics and the theory of special relativity, and nonlocal quantum information transfer without superluminal signalling and communication.

The current quantum communication is restricted by quantum superposition and quantum collapse. So now quantum communication is not quantum entangled communication, but quantum encrypted communication, which is based on the BB84 protocol (Bennett, et al. 1984), which is quantum

cryptographic distribution protocol, and uses the polarization state of photons to transmit information. And the basis of these is still the general quantum mechanics. Siddiqui, et al. (2014), proposed a new Quantum Key Distribution method, which provides an additional layer of security over the standard BB84 protocol.

So far, the basic entangled communication schemes proposed are mainly to establish direct relations between two entangled particles, and it is generally believed that there is not superluminal communication. For example, a typical method prepares a pair of entangled photons at the A, leaving the photon 1, the photon 2 sent to the B position. If A wants to send a message to B, it has to measure photon 1 and then tell B to make the measurement by means of classical communication.

In 2002, Bose and Home (2002) proposed that used sorter sends two entangled particles. Hao, et al. (2021), researched the entanglement-assisted communication surpassing the ultimate classical capacity. Hu, et al. (2021a,b), discussed long-distance entanglement purification for quantum communication, and pathways for entanglement based quantum communication.

Its important basis is that Galvez, et al. (2010), proposed a complete set of instruments to generate entangled photons in the laboratory, and the experimental process into a manual placed on the network.

Simple Superluminal Entangled Communication Scheme

We researched the theoretical method of entangled communication (Chang 2021), which is to establish two mutually entangled particles or devices Alice ($\uparrow\textcircled{1}\downarrow$) and Bob ($\downarrow\textcircled{2}\uparrow$) (Fig.1). As long as observing the information of A position can know the corresponding results of the other B. The key is not to send information each other, but to observe-control self results, thus knowing another information and phase. It is consistent with First Laser-Amplified Superluminal Hookup (FLASH) proposed by Herbert (1982), but which restricts by quantum mechanics. The experiment achieves the spacelike separation of the observations (Weihs

et al. 1998), and the corresponding superluminal phase velocity. While sending information, check-compare results in both places must depend on the intermediate station Cart (3), which is still the time-like interval, subluminal and Lorentz transformation (LT).

Figure 1. Relations between Three Positions

Between A and B there is the nonlocal superluminal correlation and the phase velocity, which is a very predictable name. The relation between group velocity and phase velocity is the well-known de Broglie relation $v\bar{v} = c^2$. It is a post-processing. If continuous sending of different entangled particles to A and B, it will be confidential, and corresponds to constant modification of the key. The key difference is that involve not 3 groups of particles, but only a pair of entangled particles and a pair of entangled devices.

A pair of entangled states is generated on both positions, or preparing and transmitting a pair of entangled instruments, so the superluminal quantum communication can be realized. Thus encoding the states (different phases) to form two codes: yes or no, \uparrow (positive) or \downarrow (opposite), both correspond to 1 or 0. Manipulation for one position can pass the same message or information to the other, so we may implement the superluminal communication. If they are always opposite (e. g. spin-polarization), for 11001 at A, B will be 00110. If both are the same (similar magnetic direction), A and B are all 11001. Of course, they must be completely entangled.

For the signature r , let $r = e^{-i\pi\alpha}$, $r=1$ so the signature exponent $\alpha = 0$, $r=-1$ so $\alpha = 1$.

Further, it develops to the corresponding information theory. From this, a popular example is the telepathy between A and B.

Complete Special Relativity as Base of Superluminal Communication

Based on the classification of the timelike and spacelike intervals, which may derive two symmetrical topological structures separated by the light-cone:

A. The timelike interval $s^2 = r_{mn}^2 - c^2 t_{mn}^2 < 0$; the speed defined as $|v| = |r_{mn} / t_{mn}| < c$ (subluminal); the time dilation must be at the same space position, $x=0$, from which $s^2 = x^2 - c^2 t^2 = -c^2 T^2$, and $t = T / \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$.

B. The spacelike interval $s^2 = r_{mn}^2 - c^2 t_{mn}^2 > 0$; the speed defined as $|v| = |r_{mn} / t_{mn}| > c$ (superluminal); the length contraction must involve only one time instant, $t=0$, from which $s^2 = l_0^2 - c^2 t^2 = R^2$, and $R = l_0 \sqrt{1 - (c/\bar{v})^2}$.

The above states do not require the Lorentz transformation. The special relativity itself does not, and cannot, restrict velocity absolutely, and does not exclude the spacelike interval and the superluminal (Chang 1989, 2013a).

Based on the basic principles of the special relativity, according to the constancy of the velocity of light in the vacuum principle, it obtains invariance:

$$s^2 = r_{mn}^2 - c^2 t_{mn}^2 \tag{1}$$

In a time-space $(x_0 - x_1)$ plane, a universal transformation of the special relativity is:

$$x_1' = x_1 \operatorname{ch} \varphi - x_0 \operatorname{sh} \varphi \quad (2)$$

$$x_0' = x_0 \operatorname{ch} \varphi - x_1 \operatorname{sh} \varphi \quad (3)$$

When one adds an independent hypothesis: At the same space position (for example, the origin of K' frame, or for rest point, etc.), namely the premise $x_1'=0$ always exists. So from (1) $\operatorname{th} \varphi = x_1 / x_0 = v / c$ is obtained, then we derive the Lorentz transformation (LT):

$$x_1' = \gamma(x_1 - vt), t' = \gamma(t - vx_1 / c^2), \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$. Various approaches of introducing the Lorentz transformation, without exception and unanimously, applied this similar hypothesis! Such the spacelike interval has been excluded. LT naturally has the restriction that any velocity cannot be larger than the speed of light c .

When we give up this hypothesis, then besides (4), another symmetrical system exists yes. So long as the simultaneity $t'=0$ holds, from (3) $\operatorname{th} \varphi = x_0 / x_1 = c / \bar{v}$ is obtained, then we derive necessarily the generalized Lorentz transformation (GLT) (Chang 1989, 2013a):

$$x_1' = \bar{\gamma}(x_1 - c^2 t / \bar{v}), t' = \bar{\gamma}(t - x_1 / \bar{v}), \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\gamma} = 1 / \sqrt{1 - (c/\bar{v})^2}$. LT and GLT are connected by the de Broglie relation $v\bar{v} = c^2$, in which v is group velocity and soliton velocity, and \bar{v} is phase velocity, which must be superluminal. Phase as a state in \bar{v} is a very

magic definition. The superluminal GLT may solve many problems on $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ and the simultaneity.

Further, we supposed that the special relativity principle holds among the inertial systems, and introduce the two inertial systems K and K' , whose relative speed is u (Chang 1989, 2013a). Then for an origin O'

$$x' = (x - ut) / \theta(-u) \quad (6)$$

For another origin O

$$x = (x' + ut') / \theta(u) \quad (7)$$

Using the special relativity principle or the isotropy of space $\theta(-u) = \theta(u)$, from (6) and (7) we obtain

$$t' = \{t - [1 - \theta^2(u)] \frac{x}{u}\} / \theta(u) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dx'}{dt'} = v' = (v - u) / \{1 - [1 - \theta^2(u)] \frac{v}{u}\} \quad (9)$$

We introduce the K'' system whose speed is v relative to K , so the speed of K'' is v' relative to K' . From the same reason for the origin O'

$$\frac{dx''}{dt''} = -v' = (u - v) / \{1 - [1 - \theta^2(v)] \frac{u}{v}\} \quad (10)$$

Eqs.(9) and (10) are compared, and then we derive $[1 - \theta^2(u)](v/u) = [1 - \theta^2(v)](u/v)$. Using the separation of variables

$$[1 - \theta^2(u)]/u^2 = [1 - \theta^2(v)]/v^2 = k, \quad (11)$$

where the quantity k is a universal constant that is independent of relative speeds u and v . Because θ is dimensionless, the dimension of k is the same with $1/u^2$. Such we can assume that $k = 1/c_h^2$. Since it cannot be determined that c_h is speed of something by the logical way, we may only suppose that c_h is an arbitrary invariable speed, so

$$\theta(u) = \sqrt{1 - ku^2} = \sqrt{1 - (u/c_h)^2}. \quad (12)$$

From (6) and (7) we obtain the extensive Lorentz transformation (LT) of $c \rightarrow c_h$,

$$x' = \frac{x - ut}{\sqrt{1 - (u^2/c_h^2)}}, t' = \frac{t - (ux/c_h^2)}{\sqrt{1 - (u^2/c_h^2)}}. \quad (13)$$

The special relativity principle derives necessarily the invariance of a certain velocity, and the constancy-principle of this velocity (Chang 1989, 2013a). In fact, some methods of derivation of the LT are universal, and do not require the constancy of the velocity of light (Pauli 1958; Lee et al. 1975; Levy-Leblond 1976). For example, Lee and Kalotas presented that a method derives the LT by the principle of relativity alone, without resorting to the existence of a universal limiting velocity (Lee et al. 1975). Therefore, the two basic principles of the special relativity are not independent one another, and are not complete on equality. The exact basic principles of the special relativity should be redefined more suitably as (Chang 1989, 2013a): I. The special relativity principle, which derives necessarily an invariant speed c_h . II. Suppose that the invariant velocity c_h in the theory is the velocity of light in the vacuum c .

Einstein pointed out the relativity of space and time. It should be universal, and does not depend on the particular constancy of the velocity of light. Only based on the special relativity principle or various equivalent principles, one may derive the extensive LT, and the universal velocity invariance. It is called the extensive special relativity, in which only $c \rightarrow c_h$ (another invariant velocity). It includes the classical Newtonian theory of $c_h = \infty$, and the special relativity of $c_h = c$. But many experiments shown that the velocity is not infinite (Lee et al. 1975).

The velocity c_h is invariant, and $ds^2 = dx_\alpha^2 - c_h^2 dt^2$ is also an invariable quantity.

But, c_h may not be the velocity of light in the vacuum, so it is relative, and may be different values for different regions. The extensive special relativity bases only on the special relativity principle. The second principle in the special relativity is a concrete c_h . Even if it is shaken by some new experiments, the formulations of this theory will be able to be not also changing greatly. We cannot but wonder with admiration that the special theory of relativity is really a full beautiful and very universal theory. If the measurements have error, even the velocity of light is not constancy, it is also possible that the extensive special relativity holds still.

If the second principle does not hold, for example, the superluminal motions exist, the theory will be still the extensive special relativity, in which the formulations are the same, only c is replaced by the invariant speed $c \rightarrow c_h$. So LT is unsuitable for photon and neutrino, the photon transformation (PT) is unified for space $x' = r + ct$ and time $t' = t + (r/c)$ from the light-cone. It may reasonably overcome some existing difficulties, and cannot restrict that the rest mass of photon and neutrino must be zero. LT, GLT and PT together form a complete structure of the Lorentz group. Moreover, we discussed that if the invariant speed c_h are various invariant

velocities, the diversity of space-time will correspond to many worlds (Chang 1989,2013a). Moreover, we proved (Chang 2013) that the local Lorentz transformations for different systems cannot derive the varying speed of light (VSL) theory searched warmly (Albrecht et al. 1999; Mogueijo 2000,2001). VSL is probably connected only with the general relativity.

At present, loophole-free Bell inequality violation using electron spins is separated by 1.3 km (Hensen et al. 2015). Energy-time entangled photon pairs violate Bell inequalities by photons more than 10.9 km (Zbinden et al. 2001) and 12.4 km (Pan et al. 1998). Further, quantum teleportation is over 100 km, 143 km and 1200 km (Yin et al. 2012,2017; Ma et al. 2012). Some physicists proposed that their entangled distance is infinite, and even is an action at a distance. I think, the quantum entangled state is probably a new fifth interaction (Chang 2013a). Its strength seems to obey neither the Newtonian long-range gravitational law nor the short-range strong-weak interactions.

Some physicists (Bell, Eberhard, Bohm and Hiley) suggested that quantum correlations could be due to superluminal communications (tachyons) that propagate isotropically with velocity $v > c$. For finite values of v , quantum mechanics and superluminal models lead to different predictions. Some years ago a Geneva group and Cocciaro group did experiments on entangled photons to evidence possible discrepancies between experimental results and quantum predictions. Cocciaro, et al. (2018), searched superluminal quantum communications on recent experiments and possible improvements. But, no evidence for these superluminal communications has been obtained. Entanglement experiments have confirmed that the superluminal action is true (Gao 2004,2014; Walleczek, et al. 2016; Cocciaro et al. 2018), therefore, this must apply GLT. Conversely, it can test GLT.

There is not randomness between entanglement, but rather general quantum correlations. Further, scientists have long discovered quantum correlations, with two or more particles in a particular system always showing the same state even far apart. When one of the quantum

states changes, the other quantum changes accordingly. Such this scheme may extend to that $\langle A|$ and $|B\rangle$ are quantum correlations, or general correlations.

So far, nonlocality is generally called spooky action at a distance. Such it is believed that the entangled states do not transmit information, but affect each other instantly. We supposed that it is similar to electromagnetic field, which is a type of Laplace field (demon). It may apply to the superluminal communication. In a word, entanglement seems to be a particular synchronism.

In a word, based on the EPR prediction, the nonlocality and entangled state become the frontline in modern physics. We discussed the phase of the entangled field, whose phase particle (phason) has some characters and corresponding equations. It is tachyon, and assume that it is similar to photon with $J=1$ and $m=0$ or mass is very small as similar neutrino, and may show the action at a distance. We researched that this field as wave has some characters, and the superluminal quantum communication by a pair of entangled states is generated on both positions, or by preparing and transmitting a pair of entangled instruments. Manipulation for one position can pass the same message or information to the other, so we may implement the superluminal communication. Assume that the entangled field has a similar magnetic theory, which may be a quantum cosmic field, or be the extensive quantum theory, or God or the Buddha-fields and so on. These are all macroscopic fields, which correspond to de Broglie-Bohm nonlinear "hidden variable" theory, but it is microscopic (Chang 2019).

Moreover, the exact quantum communication seems to be inconsistencies with the quantum non-cloning theorem (Wotters et al. 1982). Further, Barnum, et al. (1996), proposed the quantum non-broadcasting theorem. It should be related to the duality quantum computer (Long 2006; Gudder 2007). Superluminal may be the Einstein-Rosen bridge as the wormhole.

Einstein pointed out: "Logic will get you from A to B, imagination will take you everywhere". We believe study and application of nonlocality and

entangled field have important scientific and social significance (Chang 2019).

Nonlocality, Entangled Field and Its Predictions

From the EPR prediction, the nonlocality and entangled state become the frontline in modern physics. We proposed that the entangled states must obey GLT because of they possess the superluminal and some characters as the spacelike vectors. It changes the phase of the entangled field, whose phase particle (phason) has some characters and corresponding equations. It is tachyon, and assume that it is similar to photon and $J=1$ and $m=0$ or mass is very small as similar neutrino, and may show the action at a distance. We researched that this field as wave has some characters. Assume that the entangled field has a similar magnetic theory, which may be a quantum cosmic field, or be the extensive quantum theory, or God or the Buddha-fields and so on. These are all macroscopic fields, which correspond to de Broglie-Bohm nonlinear "hidden variable" theory, but it is microscopic. In a word, study and application of nonlocality and entangled field have important scientific and social significance (Chang 2019).

Further, we researched some possible theories of the entangled states and corresponding predictions (Chang 2019):

Entangled Relativity and Predictions

Since the quantum entangled state possesses some characters, for example, coherency, nonlocality and superluminal, etc., we propose that it may and must apply the complete special relativity (CSR) and GLT (Chang 1989, 2013a).

From Eq.(1) we derive $s^2 = r_{mn}^2 - c^2 t_{mn}^2 > 0$ for the spacelike interval, the speed defined as $|v| = |r_{mn} / t_{mn}| > c$ is always superluminal. If we choose an inertial frame that $t'_{mn} = 0$ (the simultaneity), the phase velocity will be $|\bar{v}| = \infty$, i.e., the action at a distance. In the spacelike interval the mass should be $m = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - (c/\bar{v})^2}$.

The quantum entangled states are related to space-time, which form the entangled fields. Their chances are the superluminal phase velocities, and as the spacelike vectors possess some fundamental characteristics in any four-vectors (Chang 1989, 2013a):

$(P; E/c)$	$(j; c\rho)$	$(A; \varphi)$	$(k; \omega/c)$	$(dk; d\omega/c)$	$(w_\alpha = \frac{\gamma}{c^2} \frac{d(\gamma v)}{dt}; w_0 = \frac{\gamma}{c} \frac{d\gamma}{dt})$
$P=mv > E/c$	$j = \rho v > c\rho$	$A > \varphi$	$k > \omega/c$	$dk > d\omega/c$	$w_\alpha < w_0$

Here P is momentum, and E is energy, etc. Because $\omega/k = \bar{v}$ is phase velocity, $(k; \omega/c)$ is usually a timelike vector with $\bar{v} > c$. While $d\omega/dk = v$ is group velocity, so $(dk; d\omega/c)$ is usually a spacelike vector with $c > v$. Usual the timelike and spacelike intervals are two topological separated parts by the light-cone.

In the timelike vectors, only x, p, j, A, k, dk and w_α can be zero, and then LT is derived. In the spacelike vectors, only t, E, $\rho, \varphi, \omega, d\omega$ and w_0 can be zero, then GLT is derived. In this case φ

$= 0$, but $A \neq 0$; $\rho = 0$, but $j \neq 0$, etc. These are some predictions based on CSR. Mariwalla let $E=0$, so GLT of the four-vector $(p; E/c)$ was derived.

For any four-vector $(A; A_0)$, its LT is

$$A_1' = \gamma(A_1 - vA_0/c), A_0' = \gamma(A_0 - vA_1/c), \tag{14}$$

and GLT is

$$A_1' = \bar{\gamma}(A_1 - cA_0/\bar{v}), A_0' = \bar{\gamma}(A_0 - cA_1/\bar{v}) \quad (15)$$

Both possess the most perfect symmetrical form. Only A_1, A_0 interchange each other between A_1 and A_0 representations, and LT (4) and GLT (5) also interchange from v/c to c/\bar{v} .

The entangled field is in the spacelike interval, so the area is larger and the possibility is more.

Entangled Quantum Theory and Predictions

The quantum representations on the entangled fields are known, in which two basic spin states

are quantized $|\frac{1}{2}\rangle$ and $|\frac{-1}{2}\rangle$, and group of two particles are (S^A, S^B) , so there are four eigen-states:

$$\begin{aligned} &|\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B, \quad |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_B, \quad |\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B, \\ &|\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_B \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

While the coupling represents are:

$$SX_{SM} = MX_{SM} (S = S^A + S^B) \quad (17)$$

For $S=0$ and $M=0$,

$X_{00} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [|\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_B - |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B]$ is single state.

For $S=1$ and $M=0, \pm 1$,

$$X_{10} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [|\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{-1}{2}\rangle_B + |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B]$$

$$X_{11} = |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B \quad \text{and} \quad X_{1-1} = |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B$$

are threefold states. Here X_{00}, X_{10} are two entangled states. X_{11}, X_{1-1} carry through equal

weight superposition, it may compose four entangled states:

$$|\psi^\pm\rangle_{AB} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [|\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B \pm |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B] \quad (18)$$

$$|\phi^\pm\rangle_{AB} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [|\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B \pm |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_A |-\frac{1}{2}\rangle_B] \quad (19)$$

This derives the non-locality, and is similar to the Bell basis in quantum mechanics. It is the entangled state of quantum theory, and may describe quantum teleportation (Bouwmeester, et al. 1997).

The entanglement is probably a new field, and exchanges tachyon or phase particle (phason), which corresponds to change of phase. They each other are the phase velocities. Its character is tachyon, and assume that it is similar to photon and $J=1$ and $m=0$ or mass is very small as similar neutrino. It shows the action at a distance.

Assume that the entangled field has the wave-particle duality, from which we propose its quantum theory: They are bosons, and based on the same energy-momentum relation:

$$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 \quad (20)$$

we derive Klein-Gordon equation of quantum mechanics:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x_\mu^2} - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0 \quad (21)$$

When $m_0=0$, it is Maxwell equation. The Schrödinger equation is:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi. \quad (22)$$

It agrees with the complete relativity, and is a quantum theory of the complete relativity.

Quantum entanglement corresponds possibly to the nonlinear superposition principle (Chang 1989, 2014a). These are also some predictions based on the similar quantum theory of entangled fields.

Maudlin (2002,2011) researched the quantum nonlocal entanglement and special relativity in modern physics.

Entangled Waves and Predictions

The entangled fields possess the wave property. It is known that two entangled fields can interfere each other. They should diffract from each other, or even reflect. Especially combined quantum theory it will have the barrier penetration.

At the same time, wave may further develop to the field. It may combine the mechanical wave theory (Chang 2014b). Such Schrödinger equation may develop to following nonlinear equations:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \alpha \psi \nabla \psi = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi; \quad (23)$$

and a similar KdV equation:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \sigma \psi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3}. \quad (24)$$

From Boussinesq equation and Klein-Gordon equation we may develop similarly to the nonlinear equation:

$$\phi_{tt} - \phi_{xx} = \sigma(\phi^2)_{xx} + \phi_{xxxx}. \quad (25)$$

Further, many phase spaces exist probably in our world, for example, body-mind-spirit and they

are entangled each other. The extensive quantum entanglement is a real “spooky action at a distance” (Einstein). Entangled states in parapsychology can explain synchronization, telepathy as resonance of the thought field (Chang 2003,2018c), and the unification of men and nature, etc. In quantum mechanics, the participant in the Wheeler interpretation is the unification of men and nature. Combined animism, it can be further explained prediction, premonition and other phenomena of parapsychology. The same frequency of the thought field is easy to synchronize. Quantum entanglement among living things produces their synchronization and magic special functions.

So far, it is generally believed that the entangled states do not transmit information, but affect each other instantly. We suppose that it is similar to electromagnetic field, and may apply to the superluminal communication. In a word, entanglement seems to be a particular synchronism.

A pair of entangled states is generated on both positions, or preparing and transmitting a pair of entangled instruments, so the superluminal quantum communication can be realized. Thus encoding the states (different phases) to form two codes: yes or no, \uparrow (positive) or \downarrow (opposite), both correspond to 1 or 0. Manipulation for one position can pass the same message or information to the other, so we may implement the superluminal communication. Further, it develops to the corresponding information theory.

Its important basis is that Galvez, et al. (2010), proposed a complete set of instruments to generate entangled photons in the laboratory, and the experimental process into a manual placed on the network.

Musser searched the spooky action at a distance as the phenomenon that reimagines space and time, and what it means for black holes, the Big Bang and theories of everything (Musser 2015). He proposed that the nonlocality exists widely in black holes, the cosmic macrostructure and particle collisions (Musser 2015). Jacques (2007), Kaiser (2012) and Peruzzo, et al. (2012), realized the delayed-choice experiments.

The quantum entangled state possesses some new characters, such as coherency, nonlocality, quantum teleportation and superluminal, and may apply GLT. We proposed that it is probably a new fifth interaction. Some physicists proposed that their entangled distance is infinite, and even is an action at a distance. I think, it is middle-rang, and neither infinite nor very short. From this five interactions may be exhibited completely in Fig.2 (Chang 2013a).

Figure 2. Relation among Five Interactions

The quantum entangled state as the new interaction will be a special place at a middle state among the known four interactions, and seems to be fully enlightening meaning. Such the fifth interaction is very mystic, which is called spooky action at a distance by Einstein.

We proposed that the entangled fields may be developed by a similar magnetic field (Chang 2019).

First, the magnetic induction seems to be transient transmission, in which $A \neq 0$, but $\varphi = 0$. It presupposes that there should be a large external field similar to the geomagnetic field. This may be a quantum cosmic field, whose wave function of Universe obeys the Wheeler-de Witt equation:

$$(\eta^2 G_{ijkl} \frac{\delta}{\delta g_{ij}} \frac{\delta}{\delta g_{kl}} + \sqrt{G^3} R)\psi(g) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Here
$$G_{ijkl} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{G}} (g_{ik} g_{jl} + g_{il} g_{jk} - g_{ij} g_{kl})$$

If a similar magnetic field exists, it will be the rotation field, whose equations are:

$$\oint_s B dS = 0, \text{ and } \nabla B = 0. \quad (27)$$

Such it may be used and analogous to communication. Probably, these fields are the origin of the entangled field, the entanglement is only a result.

Further, we should try to find a magnetic monopole. If we find a similar charge, the theory will be developed to the similar electrodynamics, in which Maxwell equations are:

$$\frac{\partial F_{lm}}{\partial x_k} + \frac{\partial F_{mk}}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial F_{kl}}{\partial x_m} = 0, \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{\partial F_{ik}}{\partial x_k} = \frac{4\pi}{c} j_i. \quad (29)$$

Lorentz equation is:

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = e(-grad\varphi - \frac{\partial A}{c\partial t} + \frac{v}{c} \times rotA) = e(E + \frac{v}{c} \times H) \quad (30)$$

Third, we may develop a similar magnetohydrodynamics. Fourth, combining quantum mechanics, it derives a similar quantum electrodynamics (QED). Fifth, combining general relativity, it derives the electromagnetic general relativity (Chang 2005).

Discover these fields and their corollaries are also our predictions. The general predictions include the telepathy and the induction between men and nature, etc.

The earliest entangled state originated from the induction and unification between men and nature in the Chinese traditional culture.

In a word, study and application of nonlocality

and entangled field have important scientific and social significance.

We researched some new possible developments of time and space, such as the fractal dimension extended to the complex dimension, the higher dimensional time, and the arrow of time. A generalized Noether's theorem is proposed. In quantum theory, we searched the higher dimensional complex space in supersymmetry, and the space-time operators. Quantum entanglement is probably new fifth interaction (Chang 2022a).

This scheme is combined between the special relativity and quantum theory.

Extensive Quantum Theory

Quantum entanglement and quantum communication are all some macroscopic phenomena. But, the some applications of quantum, such as sociology and economics, etc., have the scale question.

Great physicist Feynman (1966) pointed out: "There are certain situations in which the peculiarities of quantum mechanics can come out in a special way on large scale." In a special situation "quantum mechanics will produce its own characteristic effects on a large or 'macroscopic' scale". Since 1989 we proposed the extensive quantum theory: We developed the Titius-Bode (TB) law describes approximately the average distances between the Sun and various planets in the solar system to a new form (Chang 1990,2002):

$$r_n = an^2, \quad (31)$$

where a is a constant and n is integer. Let $a=0.042$ (astronomical unit) for the terrestrial planets, $a=1.2$ for the Jovian planets, so n are continuous natural numbers, and obtained results tally with distances of planets. It has a similarity between the solar system and the Bohr model, both are respectively based on long-range gravitational field and electric field between nuclei and electrons, we developed a quantum theory of the solar system. Further, assume that the extensive quantum theory is suitable for

man, cell and macromolecule. We proposed its three laws: 1. Extensive quantum is its element in any system. 2. Its theory has similar quantum formulations with different quantum constants H . 3. Evolutions of systems may be continuous, but stable states are quantized. Its mathematical base is fractal (Chang 2018b). This is not only microscopic, but also applicable to the macro fields. It is applied to many aspects, including astronomy (Chang 2002), physics (Chang 2013b,2022b), biology (Chang 2012,2015a), parapsychology (Chang 2018c,2020), sociology (Chang 2023) and economics (Chang 2025,2026).

In 2025 Nobel Prize in Physics three winner J. Clarke, M.H. Devoret and J.M. Martinis affirmed the existence of macroscopic quantum effects.

Based on the analysis of the logical structure of quantum mechanics, we proposed that the wave-particle duality is the only basic principle of quantum mechanics. Statistics is the corresponding mathematical character. The other principles are all its physical or mathematical results, which includes the uncertainty principle (Chang 2018a).

We assume that the extensive Schrödinger equation is:

$$iH \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{2m} H^2 \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi \quad (32)$$

Its time-independent Schrödinger equation ($H=1$) is:

$$\frac{d^2 \psi}{dr^2} + 2m(E - V)\psi = 0 \quad (33)$$

Assume that the potential is a harmonic oscillator:

$$V(r) = \frac{1}{2} Kr^2 \quad (34)$$

Such the quantum energy levels are:

$$E_n = H\nu\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right), n=0,1,2,\dots \quad (35)$$

They can derive quantization of various systems.

Various applications of mathematical and physical method are the important developing direction of modern social sciences. We researched the nonlinear sociophysics and the nonlinear whole sociology, which have chaos, fractal, etc., and discussed the quantum sociology, whose bases are the extensive quantum theory and the social individual-wave duality (Chang 2015b).

Since the entire economic system exhibits profound quantum characteristics, we proposed the extensive quantum economics, which governed by three fundamental principles: 1. Duality, individuals act as particles, while collectively forming waves (Chang 2015b). Economic development and prices in market economy have all wave property. 2. The uncertainty principle (Nordhaus 2013; Hansen et al. 2015) governs both macro and micro scales, with equilibrium being transient. Money is a classic measure of uncertainty (Orrell 2018). 3. The extensive statistics. Many economic systems have randomness, for which the most similar physical theory is general quantum theory. Moreover, quantum entanglement may occasionally manifest. Further, we may apply quantum principles, theory and mathematical equations to economics. The corresponding Schrödinger equation and its potentials are studies, in which different potentials correspond to different economic policies and development models in quantum economics, and form different results and varying energy levels. We discuss some economic models, such as the nonlinear theory of economic growth and the multiply connected topological economics, etc., and proposed a specific prediction method (Chang 2025).

Conclusion

Since quantum theory has rich mathematical and

physical contents, so it not only may be applied to many regions, and theory may also be corrected and developed.

We propose that a simple superluminal entangled communication scheme is combined between the complete special relativity and quantum theory. This will promote development of quantum theory and relativity. Editor of Asian Journal of Research and Reviews in Physics think that we proposed the superluminal communication scheme based on quantum entanglement (Chang 2021), which is revolutionary.

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